

AZORES DEEPSEA RESEARCH

**MAPGES 2025 PHYSETER CRUISE REPORT: EXPLORATION AND MAPPING OF DEEP-SEA
BIODIVERSITY IN THE AZORES ON-BOARD THE MT PHYSETER**

INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGAÇÃO EM CIÊNCIAS DO MAR - OCEANOS, UNIVERSIDADE DOS AÇORES, HORTA, PORTUGAL

MAPGES 2025 CRUISE REPORT: EXPLORATION AND MAPPING OF DEEP-SEA BIODIVERSITY IN THE AZORES ON-BOARD THE MT PHYSETER

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Date: 29 September 2025

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1	SUMMARY OF THE MAPGES 2025 CRUISE ON-BOARD THE MT PHYSETER	1
1.1	Main objectives.....	1
1.2	Methodology.....	1
1.3	Statistics.....	2
1.4	Cruise summary.....	3
1.5	Main achievements.....	5
1.6	Stations surveyed during MapGES 2025 cruise onboard the MT Physeter.....	6
1.7	Cruise diary of MT Physeter Leg 1a.....	6
1.8	Cruise diary of MT Physeter Leg 1b.....	8
1.9	Cruise diary of MT Physeter Leg 1c.....	22
2	“LIFE” ON BOARD MT PHYSETER DURING MAPGES 2025	24
2.1	“Life” on board MT Physeter during MapGES 2025 Leg1 a, b ,c.....	24
3	ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	29

1 SUMMARY OF THE MAPGES 2025 CRUISE ON-BOARD THE MT PHYSETER

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1.1 MAIN OBJECTIVES

MapGES 2025 continues our longstanding commitment to map deep-sea biodiversity and identifying Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs) in the Azores with the Azor drift-cam imagery system. Our 2025 expedition aimed to enhance the data collected in previous surveys by conducting new video transects along the slopes of several islands in the archipelago, including Faial, Pico, Graciosa and Terceira. This fieldwork focused mostly on under-sampled areas and deeper strata. Additionally, we planned to explore one new area, specifically Vasco Gil seamount. Our ultimate goal is to achieve a comprehensive understanding of the deep-sea fauna dwelling on the slopes, banks, and seamounts in these areas. Like previous MapGES cruises, our objectives included: (i) mapping benthic communities in previously unexplored seamounts, ridges, and island slopes; (ii) identifying new areas that meet the FAO definition of Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems; and (iii) determining the distribution patterns of deep-sea benthic biodiversity in the Azores. The results of this cruise added to the previous contributions to identify the environmental drivers that determine the spatial distribution of deep-sea benthic biodiversity in the Azores. It also provides valuable information in the context of Good Environmental Status (GES), Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) and new insights on how to sustainably manage deep-sea ecosystems.

1.2 METHODOLOGY

We conducted several underwater video transects along the seafloor using the Azor drift-cam, a cost-effective drifting camera system developed by IMAR and Okeanos at the University of the Azores. This system is capable of recording high-quality underwater video images of the seabed, and it was deployed from the MT Phyceter. This year, the operation capabilities of the Azor drift-cam was expanded to ~1500 m depth. In each sampling area, we performed a representative number of dives using the video system, ranging from approximately 1200 m to the shallowest point of each structure. The objective was to capture underwater images that would effectively characterize the biodiversity across the entire bathymetric gradient and various substrate types. The video transects were strategically planned based on the most accurate bathymetric data available, allowing the camera system to drift from deeper to shallower regions. This methodology was designed to ensure optimal

image quality by maximizing light incidence and minimizing attenuation in the water column, a challenge typically encountered during descending transects. Each transect with the Azor drift-cam was planned for approximately 60 to 120 minutes on the seafloor, with the system drifting over benthic habitats at an average speed of 0.5 to 1 knot. Under favourable conditions, each working day facilitated 3 to 5 dives, corresponding to approximately 5 kilometres of seafloor explored daily.

Vessel:

MT Physeter

Dates:

Leg 1a: 4th June

Leg 1b: 21st June to 1st July

Leg 1c: 25th July

Scientific team:

Leg 1a: João Balsa (chief scientist), Inês Bruno, Inês Carneiro, Gabriela Cardoso, Marc Pladevall Vilavendrell

Leg 1b: Telmo Morato (chief scientist), João Balsa, Inês Bruno, Luís Rodrigues

Leg 1c: João Balsa (chief scientist), Guilherme Gonçalves, Marc Pladevall Vilavendrell, Marisa Gomes

1.3 STATISTICS

Altogether, we performed **41 dives** with the Azor drift-cam down to **1130 m depth**, covering **31 km** of the seafloor and producing more than **49 hours** of video footage of the seabed (Table 1).

Leg 1a: We performed 3 dives with the Azor drift-cam down to 1027 m depth, covering 610 m of seafloor and producing around 2 hours of video footage, 117 GB of disc space.

Leg 1b: We performed 35 dives with the Azor drift-cam down to 1070 m depth, covering 28 km of seafloor and producing around 42 hours of video footage, 2.32 TB of disc space.

Leg1c: We performed 3 dives with the Azor drift-cam down to 1130 m depth, covering 1.7 km of seafloor and producing 5 hours of video footage, 210 GB of disc space.

Figure 1. Scientific teams that participated in legs 1b (left) and 1c (right) of the MapGES 2025 Cruises on the MT Phsyeter.

1.4 CRUISE SUMMARY

The MapGES 2025 cruise aboard MT Phsyeter consisted of 1 leg, divided in 3 parts, aimed at exploring and revisiting slopes, banks, ridges, and seamounts surrounding Faial, Pico, Graciosa and Terceira Islands. A total of 40 successful dives were conducted out of 41 planned, covering 11 sampling areas. During **Leg 1a**, on the 4th of June, we performed 2 successful dives with the Azor drift-cam. These first deployments surveyed the deep-sea benthic communities dwelling on the slopes of the geomorphological structures on the north flank of Faial Island. These first dives were also a practical test to experience some add-ons on our structure, such as the external feeding of the GoPro camera, the implementation of a second spotlight, the use of a 1500m umbilical cable and the USBL system. During the **Leg 1b**, from 21st June to 1st of July, we performed 35 successful dives with the Azor drift-cam around Graciosa and Terceira Island slopes and some adjacent geomorphological structures such as Vasco Gil, Ilha Azul E and João de Melo. Several deep dives (>1000 m) were performed during this leg with no major problems across the components of the drift-cam. During the **Leg1c**, on the 25th of July, we performed 3 successful dives with the Azor drift-cam on the deeper sectors of the NW slopes in Pico Island. During this year's survey we observed diverse benthic and fish communities, from which we may highlight impressive and extensive aggregations of the primnoid corals *Narella versluysi* and *N. bellissima*, in Ilha Azul E, the notably large specimens of the octocoral *Callogorgia verticillata*, in Maçarico, the black corals *Leiopathes expansa*, in Beirada de Fora, and *Antipathes dichotoma*, in Vasco Gil. Also, an incredible and most likely record-breaking aggregation of anguilliform fishes Halosauridae was recorded at approximately 900 m depth in Graciosa S area.

Table 1. Areas surveyed during each of the legs of MapGES 2025 cruise on-board the MT Phsyeter, with information on number of dives, total distance of seafloor covered, and number of hours recording video footage on the seafloor.

Leg	Dates	Areas explored	Dives (n)	Dist. (km)	Bottom time (hh:mm)
1a	04/06/2025	Faial island slopes: Faial N	3	0.6	01:51
1b	21/06/2025 – 01/07/2025	Graciosa and Terceira islands slopes and banks: Graciosa NE, S, Vasco Gil N, Ilha Azul E, Terceira E, Beirada de Fora, Maçarico, and João de Melo	35	28.5	42:09
1c	25/07/2025	Pico island slopes: Pico NW	3	1.7	05:00
		Total	41	30.8	49:00

Figure 2. Location of the 41 video stations carried out with the Azor drift-cam during the MapGES 2025 cruise on-board the MT Physeter.

Figure 3. Some highlights of the footage recorded during the Legs 1a, 1b and 1c of MapGES 2025 on board the MT Physeter. (a) A rare glimpse of what it seems to be a white morph of a deep-sea shark of the genus *Deania*; (b) A good shot from our camera of an example of a community composed by the coral species *Narella versluysi*, *Leptopammia formosa* and the glass sponges *Regadrella phoenix* and *Pheronema carpenteri*; (c) Interesting geological setting on Vasco Gil area with the presence of several whiteish pebbles and boulders in an area with volcanic origin; (d) Sighting of a robust individual of the black coral *Antipathes dichotoma*; (e) Incredible aggregation of the Anguiliform fishes Halosauridae sp., the largest recorded with the Azor drift-cam; (f) Well preserved individuals of the family Plexauridae; (g) Concentration of the primnoid species *Narella versluysi* and *N. Bellissima*; (h) A large exemplar of the black coral *Leiopathes expansa* attached to a vertical wall; (i) Full body shot of a huge bluntnose sixgill shark (*Hexanchus griseus*); (j) A considerably big octocoral of the species *Callogorgia verticillata*; (l) Signs of biogenic structures “Lebensspuren” on the seafloor around Graciosa Island; (m) First recorded observation of a deceased shark on the seafloor with the Azor drift-cam.

1.5 MAIN ACHIEVEMENTS

1. During the MapGES 2025 survey conducted aboard the MT Physeter, **41 stations were completed** using the Azor drift-cam. The stations spanned depths ranging **from 205 to 1130 m**, encompassing a broad spectrum of marine strata. The survey covered approximately **31 km** of the seafloor and generated **more than 49 hours** of video footage for analysis. These numbers represent a big achievement considering that we successfully operated, once again, the Azor drift-cam for deep-sea exploration on board a small vessel and this year with several improvements on our system including an **umbilical cable of 1500m**, the underwater positioning system (USBL), the external power feeding of the GoPro camera and the addition of a second spotlight.
2. This year's survey aimed to complete the coverage of selected Island slopes around Faial, Graciosa, Terceira and Pico Islands. We successfully accomplished nearly all our objectives in each one of the areas re-visited and were also able to **explore the Vasco Gil seamount for the first time**.
3. For the third consecutive year of the MapGES survey onboard the MT Physeter, **no Azor drift-cam structures were lost**, despite that we were challenged by an entanglement on a lost fishing line, the unexpected encounter of the largest basaltic wall recorded with the Azor drift-cam dive (around 300m high) and an incident where the umbilical cable became entangled in the vessel's propeller.
4. As one of our key objectives this year was to explore deeper strata previously unsampled in certain areas, the drift-cam **was repeatedly deployed at depths exceeding 900 m** and performed outstandingly with minimal issues across all components.
5. Ilha Azul E exhibited impressive and **extensive aggregations of the primnoid corals *Narella versluysi* and *N. bellissima***.
6. Exploration of several areas East of Terceira Island continue to reveal interesting communities. Notably, **large specimens of the octocoral *Callogorgia verticillata* and large black corals *Leiopathes expansa*** were observed in the Maçarico area and Beirada de Fora areas, respectively.
7. The first exploration of Vasco Gil seamount revealed **large black corals *Antipathes dichotoma***.
8. Remarkable geological features were observed across the surveyed areas: around the Vasco Gil seamount a **heterogenous seafloor composed of contrasting black and white rock types suggests a complex geological origin** in this geomorphological structure. Interesting geological patterns of the seafloor was sighted in Ilha Azul E and Beirada de Fora areas, where **evidence of ancient stratification was recorded**.
9. A **deceased undetermined shark** was observed on a sandy bottom in Graciosa S area, probably resulting from fisheries discards. This marks the first recorded shark carcass during an Azor drift-cam deployment. The rarity of such observations rise questions about the visibility and persistence of large organic falls in deep-sea environments.
10. An incredible and **most likely record-breaking aggregation of anguilliform fishes Halosauridae** was recorded at approximately 900 m depth in the southern area of Graciosa Island.
11. An **unusually high number of angler fish (*Lophius piscatorius*)** was repeatedly observed along the slopes of Graciosa Island.
12. The **decapod *Cancer bellianus* was observed on top of the vase-shaped *Characella pachastrelloides* while holding another sponge**. This behaviour is likely uncommon for this species of crustacean.

1.6 STATIONS SURVEYED DURING MAPGES 2025 CRUISE ONBOARD THE MT PHYSETER

During MapGES 2025 cruise on board the MT Physeter we successfully completed a total of 40 dives out of the 41 stations attempted in 11 different sampling areas (Table 2).

Table 2. Compilation of the stations surveyed during MapGES 2025 cruise on board the MT Physeter.

Station	Location	Date	Time		Start Position		End Position		Depth (m)		Dist. (m)
			Start	End	Lat. (N)	Long. (W)	Lat. (N)	Long. (W)	Start	End	
St001	Faial N	6/4/2025	10:31:02	11:33:18	38.6618	-28.6022	38.6576	-28.6004	947	892	490
St002*	Faial N	6/4/2025	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
St003	Faial N	6/4/2025	18:17:40	19:07:17	38.6758	-28.6219	38.6747	-28.6216	1020	955	120
St004	Graciosa NE	6/21/2025	11:24:57	12:30:40	39.1249	-27.9485	39.1190	-27.9455	993	892	690
St005	Graciosa NE	6/21/2025	13:57:47	16:08:37	39.1170	-27.9553	39.1083	-27.9514	780	470	1010
St006	Graciosa NE	6/22/2025	10:42:10	10:55:03	39.1097	-27.8806	39.1086	-27.8797	1066	1036	140
St007	Graciosa NE	6/22/2025	11:50:45	13:04:45	39.1092	-27.8874	39.1032	-27.8784	979	966	1020
St008	Graciosa NE	6/22/2025	14:28:10	15:35:44	39.1169	-27.9570	39.1138	-27.9519	795	665	550
St009	Graciosa NE	6/22/2025	16:41:21	16:56:50	39.1265	-27.9849	39.1262	-27.9835	805	850	120
St010	Graciosa NE	6/22/2025	17:55:17	19:03:06	39.1039	-27.9324	39.0980	-27.9245	579	416	940
St011	Vasco Gil	6/23/2025	12:04:54	14:10:03	39.2221	-28.5078	39.2206	-28.4929	1068	995	1290
St012	Vasco Gil	6/23/2025	15:16:10	16:48:05	39.2155	-28.5518	39.2204	-28.5428	1070	966	940
St013	Vasco Gil	6/23/2025	17:38:14	18:50:23	39.2208	-28.5298	39.2176	-28.5254	1035	968	510
St014	Graciosa S	6/24/2025	9:52:30	11:31:15	38.9233	-27.9949	38.9266	-27.9819	981	707	1180
St015	Graciosa S	6/24/2025	12:29:03	14:18:55	38.9377	-28.0215	38.9347	-28.0094	963	904	1090
St016	Graciosa S	6/24/2025	15:22:33	15:50:58	38.9382	-28.0448	38.9388	-28.0421	818	844	240
St017	Graciosa S	6/24/2025	16:36:19	17:49:02	38.9547	-28.0023	38.9559	-27.9920	381	205	900
St018	Ilha Azul E	6/25/2025	11:39:01	12:45:47	38.7757	-27.7689	38.7747	-27.7581	950	902	940
St019	Ilha Azul E	6/25/2025	13:53:18	15:20:58	38.7767	-27.7688	38.7683	-27.7563	873	836	1430
St020	Ilha Azul E	6/25/2025	16:13:23	17:37:52	38.7528	-27.7290	38.7537	-27.7189	750	810	880
St021	Terceira E	6/26/2025	10:54:16	12:15:08	38.5120	-26.8624	38.5189	-26.8590	877	775	820
St022	Terceira E	6/26/2025	13:22:54	13:41:01	38.5193	-26.7870	38.5209	-26.7870	965	999	170
St023	Terceira E	6/26/2025	14:46:02	15:18:50	38.5226	-26.7944	38.5236	-26.7911	812	886	300
St024	Terceira E	6/26/2025	16:36:03	17:23:40	38.5701	-26.8609	38.5650	-26.8558	459	481	710
St025	Terceira E	6/27/2025	10:41:21	12:39:45	38.5621	-26.9216	38.5734	-26.9126	827	585	1480
St026	Terceira E	6/27/2025	13:25:00	14:53:15	38.6120	-26.9074	38.6219	-26.8869	347	319	2090
St027	Terceira S	6/27/2025	15:55:57	16:36:02	38.6071	-26.9758	38.6081	-26.9705	654	622	470
St028	Terceira E	6/27/2025	17:10:46	17:50:30	38.6238	-26.9726	38.6229	-26.9688	445	431	340
St029	Beirada de Fora	6/28/2025	11:31:50	13:20:41	38.5412	-26.7003	38.5529	-26.7030	730	411	1320
St030	Beirada de Fora	6/28/2025	14:57:14	15:45:48	38.4802	-26.5708	38.4841	-26.5764	947	767	650
St031	Beirada de Fora	6/28/2025	17:45:11	18:16:20	38.4822	-26.5744	38.4824	-26.5735	742	727	80
St032	Maçarico	6/30/2025	10:18:31	11:30:50	38.6899	-26.6508	38.6808	-26.6543	459	688	1050
St033	Maçarico	6/30/2025	12:48:54	14:54:32	38.6957	-26.5805	38.6862	-26.5844	954	777	1100
St034	Maçarico	6/30/2025	15:36:05	17:14:10	38.6838	-26.6001	38.6723	-26.6078	477	408	1440
St035	Maçarico	6/30/2025	18:36:23	18:51:22	38.7232	-26.8008	38.7218	-26.8008	559	512	150
St036	João de Melo	7/1/2025	10:58:25	13:07:40	38.4318	-27.3262	38.4253	-27.3379	741	476	1240
St037	João de Melo	7/1/2025	13:48:15	15:05:00	38.4639	-27.3458	38.4587	-27.3513	630	311	750
St038	João de Melo	7/1/2025	16:02:15	17:28:00	38.5214	-27.3854	38.5171	-27.3886	1000	773	550
St039	Pico NW	7/25/2025	09:45:47	11:11:45	38.5352	-28.2635	38.5311	-28.2623	1025	990	460
St040	Pico NW	7/25/2025	12:25:19	14:24:00	38.5459	-28.2757	38.5492	-28.2805	1001	740	550
St041	Pico NW	7/25/2025	15:23:10	16:59:15	38.5823	-28.3577	38.5800	-28.3497	1059	933	740

*Dive not valid

1.7 CRUISE DIARY OF MT PHYSETER LEG 1A

04 June 2025

The 2025 field season began abruptly with a short window of good weather, which we considered ideal for testing recent improvements to the Azor drift-cam, checking the equipment's condition, and identifying any repairs needed after the winter break. During this period, the team also reflected on possible further upgrades

to the system. The modifications made included a 1500m umbilical cable which will allow us to explore deeper areas, an external battery to feed of the GoPro camera which will allow us to make longer dives, the addition of another spotlight and the USBL system, that finally seems to work properly and that will let us improve the estimation of the real position of the drift-cam during dives.

The chosen area for this one-day mission was Faial North, an area previously surveyed but but still lacking information from deeper strata. We left Horta harbour at around 08:30, aboard MT Physerter with Norberto Serpa as our skipper, after preparing all the material that was loaded to the boat in the previous day. We performed a total of 3 dives (St001 – St003), between depths of 900 m and 1030 m. The day started with minor setbacks as both concentric lights didn't work, so we changed them to the spare ones. More serious issues followed. During the descent of the first dive, we realized that the USBL system wasn't functioning, as the local beacon was pinging, but the remote beacon wasn't replying. On the same dive, we also experienced poor image quality in the live view, which was not expected as the electric cable was new and was being used for the first time. The situation worsened during the ascent, when the live-view feed became unstable and showed interference. These problems persisted into the second dive, which we had to abort before reaching the bottom. This was our most critical issue, as the cause was difficult to pinpoint. We began by changing the USB Git-up cable, but that didn't solve the problem. We then replaced, one by one, the live-view cylinder, the AV-to-HDMI box, the Git-up housing, and the umbilical cable (at which point we discovered the spare was also not working). We even swapped the drift-cam itself, but nothing resolved the issue. After more than an hour of troubleshooting at sea, we returned to harbour around 15:30 to continue this work on land. After we had lunch all together, with MT Physerter crew, we got back to work and went to collect the live-view box used in RV Arquipélago. With that unit, everything worked without problems. Switching back to the MT Physerter's live-view box, it too worked perfectly, with better image quality than before. We concluded that the issue was likely not hardware-related, but instead due to magnetic interference or voltage irregularities. After adjusting the voltage in the live-view cylinder, the image improved. Confident in this solution, we set out again for one final dive at the same site as the second attempt, keeping the live-view system running throughout the trip to ensure stability. Our efforts were rewarded and during the last dive everything went as expected and without any problems. The live-view feed remained stable and of good quality (better than during the first dive), and the USBL system functioned correctly once we realized that the reference number of the remote beacon had been entered incorrectly, explaining the earlier failure. Both dives reached around 1000 m depth.

The seafloor was generally characterized by soft sediments with occasional rocky outcrops. The fauna present was mainly composed by large numbers of the coral *Chrysogorgia* sp., normally together with *Acanella arbuscula*, *Leptopsammia formosa*, *Pliobothrus symmetricus* and sporadic exemplars of *Candidella imbricata*. On sandy bottoms it was usual to sight the foraminiferans *Syringammina fragillissima*, and some echinoderms. A few deep-sea sharks, including one that seem to be a white *Deania* cf. *calceus*, were commonly encountered.

During the trip back, we discussed how the recent modifications had improved, or not, the system and planned the following weeks of work before returning to sea in two weeks. We arrived back in Horta harbour around 20:15 and unloaded the MT Physerter before calling it a day.

Figure 4. Location of Faial N and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 4th of June 2025.

Figure 5. Screenshots from the video footage recorded with the Azor drift-cam in Faial N, 4th June 2025.

1.8 CRUISE DIARY OF MT PHYSETER LEG 1B

21 June 2025

Today, we started the MapGES 2025 leg 1b which will cover the slopes of Graciosa and Terceira Islands, as well as the nearby seamounts such as Vasco Gil, Ilha Azul and João de Melo. We left the Horta harbour at around 06:30 heading toward Graciosa Island to conduct complementary dives in the Graciosa NE area. The journey was somewhat challenging due to the moderate North swell and wind. We arrived at the dive site around 11:00 and were able to perform 2 dives (St004-St005) during the day between 470 and 993 m of depth. Sea conditions improved towards the end of the day, offering some relief after the tiring trip. Both deployments went generally well, with natural drift and stable navigation. After the first dive, when recovering the camera, we discovered that the cylinder housing the battery for the LED light system and lasers had flooded completely. We replaced both the cylinder and the lid with connectors. The second dive went smoothly, with no equipment problems.

The bottoms in all the dives were characterized by the strong presence of soft sediments, only with a few sightings of boulders. The fauna observed was mainly composed of the Xenophyophores *Syringamina fragillissima*, dispersed sponges of the species *Hyalonema (Cyliconema) thomsonis* and holothuroids of the family Synallactidae, mostly because of the high extensions of sandy seafloor. It was also possible to observe the glass sponges *Farrea occa*, *Pheronema carpenteri* often together with the primnoid coral *Narella versluysi*. A large exemplar of the octocoral *Callogorgia verticillata* was also recorded. The bluntnose sixgill shark (*Hexanchus griseus*) was sighted as well as several fishes of the family Macrouridae and Anguiliform individuals.

We returned to land at around 16:30, docking at Vila da Praia harbour to check in at Moinho de Pedra Pomes, organize logistics, prepare for the next day, and rest after a demanding trip.

Figure 6. Location of Graciosa NE and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 21st of June 2025.

Figure 7. Screenshots from the video footage recorded with the Azor drift-cam in Graciosa NE, 21st June 2025.

22 June 2025

We left Vila da Praia harbour at around 9:30 after preparing all the material and equipment and enjoying a good breakfast at a local cafe. We headed to the area of Graciosa NE where we carried out 5 dives (St006 – St010) between 416 and 1016 m depth. The first dive of the day had to be aborted due to an unfavourable drift direction that pushed us toward a deeper area with a declining slope. For the second dive we selected a location better suited to the drift previously observed. All the four following dives worked very well in terms of drift, two of them in deep areas, around 1000 m, and the last one in a shallower sector of about 500 m. During the deployment of the third dive, the umbilical got entangled in the boat propeller, prompting our skipper, Norberto, to quickly enter the water and free it. The day was also marked by an important improvement in the USBL system: a configuration change significantly enhanced both the reliability of the positioning data and the clarity of its display. We will continue testing and refining the system in the field over the coming days.

The seafloor documented throughout the dives was mainly constituted by soft sediments, with the sporadic presence of basaltic overhangs and outcrops, and punctuated by some patches of coral rubble. In the deeper areas and with the strong presence of sand, the Xenophyophores *Syringammina fragillissima* were the most notable species. When progressively climbing to shallower depths and when some hard substrate was appearing, the bird's nest sponge *Pheronema carpenteri* was colonizing the seafloor in robust aggregations normally together with the primnoid coral *Narella versluysi*. Some other aggregations include the whip coral *Viminella flagellum*, with the common company of the vase shaped sponge *Characella pachastrelloides*, *Macandrewia azorica* and *Xestospongia topsenti*. A large *Lophius piscatorius* was spotted. Angler fishes have been a very common sighting around Graciosa Island.

We returned to Vila da Praia harbour where we ended our day with a barbecue of grilled fish on the MT Physeter, making the most of the long June daylight and the sunset.

Figure 8. Location of Graciosa NE and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 22nd of June 2025.

Figure 9. Screenshots from the video footage recorded with the Azor drift-cam in Graciosa NE, 22nd of June 2025.

23 June 2025

We started our day refuelling the MT Physter. This required waiting for the local authorities and the fuel truck to initiate the process, which delayed our departure from Vila da Praia harbour until around 10:00. Our destination was Vasco Gil, a small ridge on the edge of the Vasco Gil Depression, located 30 nautical miles west of Graciosa Island, a site we had never visited before. The transit took about 1 hour and 30 minutes, and we carried out 3 dives there (St011–St013) between 900 and 1100 m depth. The drift was initially going to SE but when the drift-cam reached the bottom the drift changed abruptly in direction to north making the dive a bit more challenging and requiring assistance from our skipper to maintain the desired trajectory. During this dive, the live-view camera was functioning but not recording, leaving us with only the high-resolution GoPro footage, which fortunately lasted nearly three hours. The second dive also required support from the skipper to adjust drift, although the natural direction aligned better with our target area. At one point, the system became stuck on a small vertical wall, but thanks to the team's experience, we were able to free it without damage. The final dive of the day was intended as a short, closing survey of the site. However, the drift was highly erratic, and even with the skipper's efforts, it was difficult to guide the system to the intended track. As a result, this dive was messy, with challenging navigation and relatively little fauna observed.

Overall, the fauna observed was typical of deep sectors. The rocky seafloor hosted several species of black corals, including *Leiopathes expansa*, large *Antipathes dichotoma*, *Phanopathes erinaceus*, and *Parantipathes hirondelle*. Other species that can be highlighted are the sponges *Hertwigia falcifera*, a large *Phakellia ventilabrum* and an aggregation of *Phakellia robusta*. The fish orange roughy *Hoplostethus atlanticus* and oreo fish *Neocyttus helgae* were sighted in all the dives performed. Interestingly, some areas of the seafloor around Vasco Gil were composed of a distinctive white rock, which is uncommon in the Azores.

We returned to Vila da Praia harbour at around 20h.

Figure 10. Location of Vasco Gil seamount and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 23rd of June 2025.

Figure 11. Screenshots from the video footage recorded with the Azor drift-cam in Vasco Gil, 23rd of June 2025.

24 June 2025

We left Praia harbour at around 08:30, heading towards Graciosa S area. Sea conditions were calm, making it a very pleasant day to work onboard. We were able to perform 4 dives (St014 – St017) between 200 and 980 m depth. Drifts were generally challenging and had to be frequently corrected by the skipper. USBL calibration was attempted onboard, but it resulted in poor gyroscope calibration and unreliable position estimates. From the third dive onwards, we decided not to use the USBL system due to the uncertainty of the data provided. No other major technical problems occurred during the day.

The seafloor was mainly characterized by basaltic outcrops, extensive patches of soft sediments and coral rubble. At the deeper sectors explored, the black corals *Leiopathes expansa* and *Antipathes dichotoma*, the sclerectinian *Madrepora oculata* and the bamboo coral *Acanella arbuscula* were the most common species. Highlight for a large aggregation of *Pleurocorallium johnsoni*, the presence of the sponge *Hertwigia falcifera* and large numbers of the glass sponge *Farrea occa*. On the shallower areas the whip coral *Viminella flagellum*, the gorgonian *Callogorgia verticillata* and sponges such as *Xestospongia topsenti* were usually observed. To

mention a school of anguilliform fishes of the family Halosauridae, one of the largest aggregations ever recorded, and the sighting of a deceased shark on a sandy bottom.

We returned to Vila da Praia in the late afternoon, where we had dinner at the local restaurant *Toma-lá-dá-cá*, followed by coffee in Santa Cruz da Graciosa.

Figure 12. Location of Graciosa S and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 24th of June 2025.

Figure 13. Screenshots from the video footage recorded with the Azor drift-cam in Graciosa S, 24th of June 2025.

25 June 2025

We checkout out from Moinho de Pedra Pomes at around 07:30 and left the batteries and personal belongings on board MT Phyceter. After a quick breakfast at Café Ilhéu and a USBL calibration on land, we departed to Ilha Azul E at around 09:15, a stop midway to our final destination, Terceira Island. During the day we performed 3 dives (St018 - St020) between 750 and 950 m depth. The main technical issue encountered was the flooding of the cylinder powering the GoPro camera, which damaged a voltage regulator. Despite a good land calibration of the USBL system, the positions obtained during the deep dives remained highly uncertain and were most likely unusable.

During the day, the system drifted mainly over hard substrates composed of basaltic outcrops, interspersed with occasional sand patches. The fauna observed was abundant and diverse, especially for the deepest areas explored. It is worth to mention the abundance of the glass sponge *Farrea occa* attached mainly to some basaltic walls, the often aggregations of *Pleurocorallium johnsoni* and *Errina atlantica*, normally together with large individuals of the sponge *Asconema fristedti*, the presence of the black corals *Leiopathes expansa* and *Bathypathes* sp., and the extensive number of colonies of the primnoids *Narella versluysi* and *N. bellissima*. A remarkable sighting was also made of a large ray, *Dipturus intermedius*.

After the final dive, we transited to Angra do Heroísmo on Terceira Island, arriving around 20:00. We closed the day with dinner at a local “tasca”, in the middle of the lively Sanjoaninas festival.

Figure 14. Location of Ilha Azul E and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 25th of June 2025.

Figure 15. Screenshots from the video footage recorded with the Azor drift-cam in Ilha Azul E, 25th of June 2025.

26 June 2025

We left Angra do Heroísmo marina at 09:10 and headed to Terceira E area. We performed 4 dives (St021 – St024) between 460 and 1000 m depth. The first dive drifted as expected, with constant assistance from the

vessel. The following three stations proved more challenging due to frequent changes in the natural drift. Dive St022 was aborted because the unstable drift prevented us from maintaining proper navigation or recording the target area. During the day, the external battery cylinder for the GoPro flooded again, resulting in the loss of another voltage regulator. One of the spotlights also stopped working and had to be removed from the structure. By this point, it was clear that the second spotlight greatly improved image quality, making its loss particularly unfortunate, especially since no spare was available for replacement.

The fauna encountered during this day was not very spectacular, normally appearing very sparse. The bottom was mainly rock, apart from the last dive of the day where most of the seafloor was soft sediment. Scarce echinoderms of the species *Cidaris cidaris* were observed, as well as punctual aggregations of the primnoids *Narella versluysi* and *N. bellissima*. To mention the presence of the scleractinian *Enallopsammia rostrata*, usually alone, the whip coral *Viminella flagellum* and some fields of the hydrocoral *Lytocarpia myriophyllum* when the bottom was sand. During one of the dives, we managed to make a very nice recording of the not so common ray *Dipturus oxyrinchus* that was swimming by.

We transited back to Angra do Heroísmo marina where we arrived at around 19:30 and started the necessary repairs that finished at around 21:00. We had dinner at Canadinha restaurant.

Figure 16. Location of Terceira E and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 26th of June 2025.

Figure 17. Screenshots from the video footage recorded with the Azor drift-cam in Terceira E, 26th of June 2025.

27 June 2025

Departing from Angra do Heroísmo harbour at about 09:00, we returned to the Terceira E area, where we planned to work throughout the day. Sea conditions were not ideal, with constant winds of around 15 knots and a choppy surface. Nevertheless, we performed 4 dives (St025 – St028) between 320 and 830 m depth, expanding seabed coverage across this large area. The last two dives of the day were challenging because of changes in the drift preventing us to reach the desired target. Following the loss of one spotlight the previous day, the Azor drift-cam was deployed with only a single spotlight. Additionally, one weight was lost during deployment of the second dive.

Across all dives, the seafloor encountered was a mix between hard rock and soft sediment. In the deepest sectors explored, the xenophyophores *Syringammina fragillissima* formed extensive aggregations on sandy bottoms while hard grounds hosted the primnoids *Narella versluysi* and *N. bellissima*, glass sponges such as *Farrea occa*, *Regadrella phoenix* and *Asconema fristedti*. In shallower depths, punctual and small gardens of a diversity of coral species were recorded, including *Acanthogorgia* spp., *Dentomuricea* aff. *meteor*, *Callogorgia verticillata*, *Paracalyptrophora josephinae* and *Viminella flagellum*. Other common species encountered were the glass sponge *Phakellia ventilabrum* and the hydrocoral *Lytocarpia myriophyllum*. Mobile fauna was abundant and very active in this area, with the observation of a large bluntnose sixgill shark *Hexanchus griseus*, several bluemouth rockfish *Helicolenus dactylopterus* and a school of *Trachurus trachurus*.

The final dive concluded at around 18:00, and we returned to Angra do Heroísmo marina at approximately 20:30.

Figure 18. Location of Terceira E and S and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 27th of June 2025.

Figure 19. Screenshots from the video footage recorded with the Azor drift-cam in Terceira E, 27th of June 2025.

28 June 2025

Today we refuel the boat and left Angra do Heroísmo harbour at around 09:30 towards Beirada de Fora area, a transit of about 2 hours. We performed a total of 3 dives (St029 – St031) between depths of 727 and 927 m. The first dive reached an impressive vertical wall, nearly 300 m high, with a real risk of the system becoming stuck. Nevertheless, the drift was good, and the dive went well overall. The Drift-Cam suffered only minor damage to the LED lights due to the steep elevation. During the second dive, we lost the live view first because of a loose connection between the live-view cable and the yellow box that converts the analog signal to digital. After securing the connection, the feed failed again—this time because the electric cable became caught in the winch and broke. We quickly rejoined the copper strands of the cable in a rough repair, just enough to continue the dive. This highlighted once again the remarkable simplicity and resilience of the Azor drift-cam system. When the dive ended, we tested all possibilities: the electrical cable, the voltage regulator, a different live-view cylinder, and even a spare live-view box, used in the RV Arquipélago. The problem likely stemmed from a discharged battery powering the yellow box, combined with a degraded electric cable producing interference and poor image quality. For the third and last dive, we used the drift-cam with the same material as the dive

before, but we changed the live view box and the electric cable. This time, all the equipment functioned correctly, with no interference. Unfortunately, the dive itself was compromised by a poor and looping drift.

The fauna observed during the dives was mostly *Pheronema carpenteri* aggregations, an unusually high number of the deep sponge *Hertwigia falcifera*, several large deep Plexaurids and a big sized *Leiopathes expansa*. During the rapid ascent of the first dive, it was possible to detect a difference in the species observed, passing from *Pheronema carpenteri* to aggregations of *Viminella flagellum* and *Acanthogorgia* spp. Interesting geological features were found in this area.

We finished the day and headed back to Angra do Heroísmo harbour. Sea conditions worsened during the return transit, making for a very choppy trip back to land.

Figure 20. Location of Beirada de Fora and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 28th of June 2025.

Figure 21. Screenshots from the video footage recorded with the Azor drift-cam in Beirada de Fora, 28th of June 2025.

29 June 2024

Bad sea conditions persisted throughout the day, with strong winds preventing us from working safely. After eight consecutive days at sea, we took the opportunity to rest.

The team spent time walking around Angra do Heroísmo, where the São João festivities were underway, had lunch at the *Doze Ribeiras* restaurant, and met with Priya, together with her filmmaker Elliot, a leading young conservationist from the DARWIN200 project who will join us for the next two days. We also met with our colleague Sofia Ramalho, from Aveiro, who came to learn how to deploy and operate the Azor Drift-Cam with the aim of potentially applying it on the mainland.

We ended the day in Praia da Vitória, which will serve as our base for the final two days of the mission.

30 June 2025

After our first night in Praia da Vitória, the team had breakfast at a local café and headed to the Maçarico area, on the east side of Terceira Island. Today we were joined onboard by Priya, Elliot, and Sofia. We left the harbour at around 09:00 and carried out a total of 4 dives (St032 – St035), between depths of 408 and 954 m. The sea conditions today were good to work with only a light breeze and swell. The first dive of the day was very calm, with a good natural drift that required almost no adjustments from the skipper. This area is known for the presence of lost fishing lines, so operations were conducted with extra caution. While transiting to the second dive site, the skipper had to disentangle fishing cables caught in the propeller. The second dive, a deeper one, had a more challenging drift and required assistance from the skipper, though the risk of entanglement was lower at this depth. The third dive was planned to for shallower grounds. Drift remained steady throughout deployment, heading south but slightly offset from the intended track. During the final dive of the day, once the Drift-Cam reached the bottom, the live-view feed began to deteriorate with heavy interference. Because this was a high-risk area due to fishing gear, we decided to end the dive early.

The deepest sectors explored showed a high prevalence of softer sediments hosting the bird's nest sponge *Pheronema carpenteri* and extensive fields of the primnoid corals *Narella versluysi* and *N. bellissima*. Climbing a bit more, the rock outcropped and it was possible to start observing large octocorals such as *Callogorgia verticillata*, several black corals of the species *Parantipathes hirondelle*, and extensions of the glass sponge *Asconema fristedti* normally together with the whip coral *Viminella flagellum*. The decapods *Chaceon affinis* and *Cancer bellianus* were surprisingly observed holding pieces of sponges, likely to be *Characella pachastrelloides* that also appeared in large sizes.

We returned to Praia da Vitória marina around 20:30.

Figure 22. Location of Maçarico and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 30th of June 2025.

Figure 23. Screenshots from the video footage recorded with the Azor drift-cam in Maçarico, 30th of June 2025.

01 July 2025

Today marked our final day of work with MT Physeter. We met at Praia da Vitória marina and split tasks: some of the team drove to Angra do Heroísmo to return the van, while others took the boat, which also needed refuelling. We departed Angra marina at around 10:00, heading towards João de Melo seamount, a transit of about one hour. Today we performed a total of 3 dives (St036 – St038) between 311 and 1000 meters. The first dive was very calm, with a natural drift leading toward the seamount summit and an easy and steadily ascending navigation. This dive lasted for more than two hours making it one of the longest ever recorded with the Azor drift-cam. The second dive was planned for shallower ground and was progressing well until the system became entangled in multiple lost fishing lines. Thanks to the team’s efforts, and the drift-cam’s oval shape, we managed to recover the equipment without damage. For the final dive of the mission, we chose to reduce risk and instead carried out a deep dive, around 1100 m. As expected at this depth, maintaining a stable drift was difficult, and the skipper had to constantly correct the vessel’s trajectory to keep us on target.

The bottom was generally composed of basaltic outcrops, or soft bottoms interrupted by some pebbles and patches of coral rubble. The fauna observed included large fields of *Narella versluysi* and *N. bellissima* as well as the presence of the bamboo coral *Acanella arbuscula*. The sponge *Pheronema carpenteri* appeared creating occasional aggregations and, in shallower sectors, it was possible to observe the whip coral *Viminella flagellum* normally together with the black coral *Parantipathes hirondelle*, *Acanthogorgia* spp., large numbers of *Leptosammia formosa* and huge vase shaped *Characella pachastrelloides*. The fish *Cyttopsis rosea* was also sighted sometimes in deep areas.

We finished the last dive at around 18:00 and began our return transit to Faial. During the crossing, we prepared the emblematic Portuguese dish *Caldeirada*, a traditional fish stew, which we enjoyed upon arrival at Horta harbour.

Figure 24. Location of João de Melo seamount E and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 1st of July 2025.

Figure 25. Screenshots from the video footage recorded with the Azor drift-cam in João de Melo seamount, 1st of July 2025.

1.9 CRUISE DIARY OF MT PHYSETER LEG 1C

25 July 2025

This short, 1-day-long, MapGES 2025 leg 1c began early in the morning, after having loaded MT Phyceter the day before. At around 08:00, we departed from Horta harbour and headed toward the northern slopes of Pico Island to explore Pico NW area. This region had previously been surveyed but lacked representative coverage of deeper strata. Throughout the day, we performed 3 successful (St039 - St041) dives across a depth range of 860 and 1130m. We first targeted the eastern-most sectors of this area, which is characterized by the typical gentle-sloping terrain of island flanks. The next two dives aimed to cover the flanks and summits of two small seamounts off Pico's slopes. Wind speeds increased steadily as the day progressed. Our colleague Margarida Durán, from the OKEANOS Institute, joined this leg to assist with operations with the Azor drift-cam. There were no major technical issues to report. Aside from a GoPro malfunction during the second dive and temporary problems with the live-view feed (quickly resolved) the day ran relatively smoothly. Lunch was even delivered at sea by a local restaurant in São Roque as part of the local festival.

From a faunal perspective, observations reflected the typically low-diversity benthic assemblages of deeper sedimentary sectors. Vast Xenophyophores' fields, *Hyalonema (Cyliconema) thomsonis* grounds, occasional echinoid aggregations and punctual observations of the decapod *Aristaeopsis edwardsianna* and white holothuroids were the most representative fauna of the day, as most of the terrain we drifted over was essentially characterized by sandy/muddy substrate. When sloping punctually increased, we managed to observe some basalt outcrops which harboured some distinct fauna, including the primnoid coral *Candidella imbricata*, the bamboo coral *Acanella arbuscula* and some black coral colonies of the species *Leiopathes expansa*. In terms of fishes and other mobile fauna, only some *Mora moro*, macrourids, eel-like fishes and one solitary squid *Mastigoteuthis* sp. were spotted overing about soft sediments.

After the last dive, we returned to Horta harbour, calling it for the day.

Figure 26. Location of Pico NW and the dives conducted with the Azor drift-cam on the 25th of July 2025.

Figure 27. Screenshots from the video footage recorded with the Azor drift-cam in Pico NW, 25th of July 2025.

2 “LIFE” ON BOARD MT PHYSETER DURING MAPGES 2025

2.1 “LIFE” ON BOARD MT PHYSETER DURING MAPGES 2025 LEG1 A, B ,C

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